

Educational Robotics for STEM: From Workshops to Curricula and Framework

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Abstract

This poster presents the outcomes of the first two years of a three-year project exploring and refining the use of educational robotics to engage young people in STEM education. It shows the development of activity plans which leverage constructionist concepts such as powerful ideas, objects to think with and the construction and sharing of personally meaningful artefacts in order to explore, test and extend understanding within STEM domains. Workshops in which these activity plans have been tested and refined, have so far engaged over 3,000 children between the ages of 7 and 18 in six European countries. Additionally, conferences and competitions for young people have been held each year where they compete and collaborate with others. These workshops and competitions have been systematically evaluated through QUAL+quant mixed methods, in order to inform the development of future activities and refinement of existing ones. Through this process we identify key components of successful educational robotics activities for STEM education. These have, in-turn, informed the design of a framework for educational robotics. The activity plans have informed the bottom-up development of a generic curriculum for educational robotics in STEM and are available on a dedicated repository. This poster presents a snapshot of each of these project outcomes.

Keywords

Constructionism; educational robotics; science; technology; engineering; mathematics; learning; STEM

Introduction

Constructionism and the use of robots in education seemingly go hand-in-hand. Yet, any review of the literature on the potential of educational robotics to engage young people in science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM), shows that it is often only lip-service that is paid to the ideas of Seymour Papert. Simply stating an activity to be constructionist, does not make it so. Educational robotics, as an area of research, is also one that cuts across various fields with academics from education, psychology, mathematics, engineering, computer science and science conducting research in this space, with various pedagogical approaches, research methods and objectives, with activities and research often implemented outside of the constraints of the traditional school system. Teachers, keen to embrace robotics in the classroom, can struggle to know how to design activities. They face pressures such as demonstrating measurable learning outcomes for individual students, siloed subject teaching and packed curricula. Should concepts be taught in advance and applied to robotics activities, should activities be structured to provide or require engagement with specific concepts to be completed, or should we allow students to explore, test and extend their own understanding in their own time and in their own way, potentially never explicitly engaging with the concept which should be learned?

The project presented in this poster aims to foster the interest in STEM and powerful ideas that children have at a young age (Lammer, et al., 2017), but is often lost as they progress through formal education and are increasingly exposed to societal pressures. In particular we are interested in the potential of educational robotics to engage all young people with STEM, particularly girls (Nugent, et al., 2010). The project involves the development and redesign of robotics tools and learning spaces for young people, implementing these and other commercially available robotics tools in workshops and competitions with over 4,000 children ages 7-18, in six European countries. The workshops and competitions have been systematically evaluated through a large-scale, QUAL+quant mixed methods research design, involving in-depth case studies in each country. This research has informed the design of new and the development of existing educational robotics activities. It has contributed to the development of activity plans which guide the design of activities and exemplify a generic curriculum for robotics. As this work matures, we aim to develop a framework for the design of educational robotics activities, which is accessible to both teachers and researchers.

Constructionist concepts such as powerful ideas, objects to think with and the construction and sharing of personally meaningful artefacts in order to explore, test and extend understanding within STEM domains, are used to underpin the design of activity plans and in-turn workshops. They also provide a way to explicitly introduce 21st Century Skills, the creative arts and creative expression in such educational robotics activities.

Activity Plans and Curricula

A standardised activity planning template acts as a common learning design instrument through which project partners design and communicate their design of educational robotics workshops to each other. The activity plan template aims to raise awareness of the key characteristics of constructionist educational robotics activities (Yiannoutsou, et al., 2017) and has developed in response to partner feedback as well as issues and opportunities highlighted in the evaluation. This template has also informed the design of a bespoke online repository of workshops for teachers and others interested in the use of educational robotics.

Activity plans, act as a mediating artefact through which various groups involved in the project such as teachers, academics, commercial partners, engineers and computer scientists, are able to share their own beliefs and experiences. They provide a way to identify and question assumptions. Ultimately, they act as a tool through which a shared understanding of the key components of the design of educational activities can be developed and expressed.

Reviewing the activity plans and other freely accessible educational robotics resources, a bottom-up approach is currently being used to organise the implemented activity plans and develop a series of generic curriculum paths, organised around STEM domains and complemented by arts, business and 21st century skills.

Workshops and Competitions

By the end of the project, activity plans will have been implemented in workshops involving more than 4,000 students in Austria, Bulgaria, Greece, Ireland, Malta and the UK, between the ages of 7 and 18. Workshops typically take place in schools during normal hours. Some workshops are held as one/two full-day events, where the normal timetable is suspended, whilst others occur over several weeks, integrated into subject specific lessons and the regular school timetable. A wide variety of robotics tools and learning environments have been used or created and integrated into the workshops, including LEGO Mindstorms, LEGO WeDo, Finch, Hedgehog (Koza et al., 2016) and also SLurtles (Girvan et al., 2013) in purpose designed virtual worlds. Workshops may be delivered by a small team including the class teacher, or delivered solely by the teacher, without any additional support. There are advantages and disadvantages to these different approaches, both in terms of learner outcomes and research.

There are a range of national and international robotics competitions for young people in Europe. This project examines the European regional Botball tournament which involves multiple rounds and different forms of competition. While teams competing against each other are the most common form of robotics

competitions, the Botball competition includes an Alliance round in which two teams collaborate to score the most points together. Alongside the competition there is also a conference for which each team prepares and delivers a paper. These often focus on technical developments or suggested improvements to the kit identified by the students and tend to focus on the engineering and technology domains.

Research

One of the primary aims of the project was to increase young people's interest and engagement in STEM subjects and careers. The research team were interested to find out about what concepts students participating in workshops and competitions learned, whether gender stereotypes were challenged and whether those who were originally not interested in STEM became interested through the activities, and why. The research explores whether there is a gender dimension to the roles students take and their participation in activities, in addition to whether children develop soft-skills. Another aim of the project was to develop multiple ways for students to engage with robotics activities and for students to take ownership of the activities they were involved in.

To evaluate whether the aims of the project have been met and to begin to answer the research questions, data collection has been ongoing throughout this project. Students involved in the workshops and competitions have been invited to participate in the research, with parental consent. A single evaluation kit is used by all partners, which provides all data collection instruments and schedules, including: pre and post workshop/competition questionnaires, interview and observation schedules, procedures for artefact collection (robots constructed, code written, drawing produced, etc) and reflective activities for teachers and students.

In the first year of the project the aim was to pilot the evaluation kit and explore existing practices, to inform the development of the framework and activity plans, which in turn would influence the design of activities in the second year of the project. Each workshop or competition was treated as a single case study. Within each case study, data was analysed using the constant comparative approach, allowing the researcher to remain open to emerging themes throughout. Single case studies could then be drawn together to allow analysis across or within countries, age groups, gender or other factors.

The second year of the project focused on the recommendations which emerged from the first year, their implementation and the impact, in addition to exploring the original research aims of the project. While analysis of the data was more focused, it remained largely interpretivist, allowing researchers to remain open to emerging codes and themes. Currently the project is in its final year, in which the data analysis has become yet more focused on a specific set of issues raised in the second year, however interpretivist approaches remain central. In addition, the third year provides an opportunity to explore the impact of the developing framework by contrasting the findings with the previous two years.

Developing a Framework

The development of an inclusive framework for the design of educational robotics activities in STEM began with a review of the literature and existing frameworks. Synthesising this work and considering it in relation to the findings of the research evaluation in years one and two, demonstrated that whilst many aspects of these frameworks were relevant, there were aspects such as team formation and modes of collaboration which were either missing or lacking insufficient detail.

Informed by the evaluation, the project team are currently developing a framework for educational robotics activities which is underpinned by constructionist ideas.

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References

- Girvan, C., Tangney, B. & Savage, T. (2013). SLurtles: A tool to support constructionist learning in Second Life. *Computers & Education* 61(1) 115-132.
- Lammer, L., Lepuschitz, W., Kynigos, C., Giuliano, A., & Girvan, C. (2017). ER4STEM Educational Robotics for Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics. In M. Merdan, W. Lepuschitz, G. Koppensteiner & R. Balogh (Eds.) *Robotics in Education Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, vol. 457. Switzerland: Springer International Publishing, 95-101.
- Koza, C., Lepuschitz, W., Wolff, M., Frank, D., & Koppensteiner, G. (2016, November). Hedgehog light—a versatile, white box educational robotics controller. In *International Conference EduRobotics 2016* (pp. 229-232). Springer, Cham.
- Nugent, G., Barker, B., Grandgenett, N., & Adamchuk, V. I. (2010). Impact of robotics and geospatial technology interventions on youth STEM learning and attitudes. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 42(4), 391-408.
- Yiannoutsou, N., Nikitopoulou, S., Kynigos, C., Gueorguiev, I., & Fernandez, J. A. (2017). Activity plan template: a mediating tool for supporting learning design with robotics In M. Merdan, W. Lepuschitz, G. Koppensteiner & R. Balogh (Eds.) *Robotics in Education Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, vol. 457. Switzerland: Springer International Publishing, 3-13. doi:10.1007/978-3-319-42975-5_1